

IPBES VA Chapter 2 - Systematic review on the conceptualizations of values / IPBES values assessment (2.1)

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Description

This review pertains to the IPBES values assessment. This systematic literature review was conducted to identify, characterize and assess, different conceptualizations of nature and its multiple values, including human-nature relationships, from different academic and socio-cultural traditions and perspectives. This review is the stage 1I of the strategy used by Chapter 2 and consists of a systematic literature evaluation of review articles indexed in Scopus from 1 January 2005 (year of the publication of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment) and until the date of the search (16 May 2019).

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic review for articles indexed in Scopus
- **Search languages:** Abstract and title in English
- **Search engine:** Scopus
- **Exact Search Date:** 16 May 2019
- **Search terms:**

```
TS= (
    TITLE-ABS-KEY ((valu* OR wellbeing OR well-being OR "quality of
                    life")AND(nature OR ecosystem OR biodiversity OR
                    landscape) OR "environmental valu*" OR "human-nature
                    relat*" OR "society-nature relat*")
    AND
        (DOCTYPE(ed) OR DOCTYPE(re))
    AND
        PUBYEAR > 2004
    AND
        SUBJAREA (ARTS OR BUSI OR DECI OR ECON OR PSYC OR SOCI OR
        ENVI OR EARTH OR MULT OR Undefined)
```

- **Sample extracted:** 7204 records

Treatment applied: Rules and screening criteria as specified in **(R1)** (analysis of title, source, keyword and abstract) were applied to the initial sample to select the relevant records for the review. This process resulted in 697 relevant records **(A)**.

- **Sample extracted:** 697 records
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Authors,
 - Author(s) ID,
 - Title,
 - Year,
 - Cited by,
 - DOI,
 - Link,
 - Affiliations,
 - Authors with affiliations,
 - Abstract,
 - Author Keywords,
 - Document Type,
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.1_04-2019_(A).csv

Treatment applied: PDFs were looked for all the records in **(A)**, the majority of which (681) were in English, while 16 were in other languages (German, French, Italian, Dutch, Spanish or Hungarian).

Regarding records with full text in English, 98 documents were not found and once with the full text, 90 sources (in English) were excluded following full-text review because they fell outside of the scope of the chapter or because they were not review articles or editorials. This left a final English language sample of 493 English language articles.

For the 16 non-English language sources, four articles were excluded because a full text could not be located, one Hungarian article was excluded due to a lack of language capacity within the assessment team, and five were found to be out of scope of the chapter. This left a total of 6 non-English records to be used.

The final sample was of 499 records **(B)**. These sources were coded by applying **(R2)** 55 codes, relating to the scope of chapter 2, while reading the full text.

- **Sample extracted:** 499 records
 - **Fields extracted (B):**
 - Authors,
 - Title,
 - Year,
 - Year2,
 - DOI,
 - Link,
 - **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.1_15_08-2019_(B).csv
-

Results of the coding process by using **(R2)** were considered to carry different analyses, in order to inform several sections in chapter 2, and especially, section 2.3.2.

In order to provide quantitative information of the prominence of the four frames in the literature, the 499 records that had information for the codes regarding the Life Framework of Nature's Values (Life Frames in general OR Living from OR Living with OR Living in OR Living as OR Other frames) (as presented in **(R2)**) were analyzed. This evidence was used to inform *section 2.3.1*. Details of the methodology used and results can be found in *Annex 2.13*.

Ninety-four records were revisited to inform *section 2.5*, since they had evidence for codes on value formation and change (as presented in **(R2)**).

Treatment applied: Based on expert knowledge, titles, abstracts and full text were revisited. Thirty-three relevant papers **(C)** were found to inform *section 2.5*.

- **Sample extracted:** 33 records
- **Fields extracted (C):**
 - Authors
 - Title
 - Abstract
 - Value Change/Formation Discussed Explicitly
 - Useful for section 2.5
- **Location and format of the data (C):** IPBES_VA_2.1_08-2020_(C).csv

Thirteen records **(D)** were found by using the snowball technique while reviewing the records in C .

The systematic review on conceptualizations of values had a code for “norms, rules, rights relative to valuation context (institutions)” (as presented in **(R2)**). Two hundred and sixty-eight records that presented evidence for this code were revisited to inform *section 2.4*.

Treatment applied: Records were re-coded following **(R3)**, allowing to identify 228 relevant records for *section 2.4 (E)*.

- **Sample extracted:** 228 records
- **Fields extracted (E):**

- Paper code,
 - Authors,
 - Title,
 - Year,
 - Source title,
 - Cited by,
 - DOI,
 - Abstract,
 - Author Keywords,
 - Norms, rules, rights relative to valuation context (Institutions)
 - Norms, rules and rights (Comments)
 - Codes 1-52 (as presented in R5).
- **Location and format of the data (E):** IPBES_VA_2.1_07-2020_(E).csv

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.1_04-2019_(A)	csv	1.8 MB	List of 697 relevant records after applying R1
B	IPBES_VA_2.1_08-2020_(B)	csv	160 KB	Final sample of 499 records coded applying (R2)
C	IPBES_VA_2.1_08-2020_(C)	csv	42 KB	33 relevant records to inform section 2.5 on value formation and change
D	IPBES_VA_2.1_08-2020_(D)	pdf	113 KB	Further evidence collected to inform section 2.5 on value formation and change by using the snowball technique
E	IPBES_VA_2.1_07-2020_(E)	csv	374 KB	228 relevant records to inform section 2.4
R1	IPBES_VA_2.1_02-2019_(R1)	txt	2 KB	Screening rules for initial sample of 7204 records
R2	IPBES_VA_2.1_05-2019_(R2)	txt	2 KB	55 codes for reviewing full text of the final sample in (B)
R3	IPBES_VA_2.1_06-2020_(R3)	pdf	148 KB	Codes used to re-code records presenting evidence on “norms, rules, rights relative to valuation context (institutions)” to inform section 2.4